

Optimal Power Flow Solution Incorporating Hybrid Conventional and Renewable Resources Using Electric Eel Foraging Optimization Algorithm

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Abstract

In recent years, metaheuristic algorithms have become the main tool in solving the Optimal Power Flow (OPF) problem due to their effectiveness in addressing complicated modern power systems. This complexity is fueled by the rise of Renewable Energy Resources (RERs) and the need to decrease greenhouse emissions. This research presents a comprehensive approach that aims to optimize the performance of power networks in the presence of thermal, wind, and Solar Photovoltaic (SPV) units. The algorithm implemented is named Electrical Eel Foraging Optimization (EEFO). It is carried out using the modified IEEE 30-bus test system. EEFO is compared alongside Kepler Optimization Algorithm (KOA) and Self-adaptive Bonobo Optimizer (SaBO). Two cases were taken into consideration. The first one is minimizing the Total Generation Cost (TGC); the second is minimizing generation cost, including the emission effects. The results show a reduction in TGC at 781.1981 \$/h and 792.6531 \$/h for the first and second cases, respectively; emissions were also decreased compared with previous studies. The findings obtained in this research show the validity of the proposed EEFO algorithm.

Keywords

Metaheuristic algorithm, Optimal Power Flow (OPF), Renewable Energy Resources (RERs), Solar Photovoltaic (SPV) and Electric Eel Foraging Optimization (EEFO)

I. Introduction

Electrical networks are considered the most sophisticated and complex systems humans have ever created. This is due to the vast area they cover, the numerous exchanges between various utilities, and the diversity in designs, scales, and equipment employed by different power companies. Engineers are required to have specific tools to evaluate and monitor the electrical grid. One of those tools is optimal power flow [1]. OPF is utilized to improve the power flow of the network by minimizing specific objective functions while maintaining an acceptable performance of the power system [2].

Apart from conventional resources, renewable energies are now the main research topic in OPF studies that aim to overcome our dependence on fossil fuels and increase the share of RERs in the energy mix. This is driven by the need to reduce CO₂ emissions to protect the environment and human health from the negative effects of greenhouse gases [3].

To solve the OPF problem, researchers have used metaheuristic algorithms as the most effective tool to integrate hybrid conventional and renewable resources into the grid in an optimal manner.

Recent studies include Success History-based Adaptive Differential Evolution (SHADE) [4], Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) [5], Jellyfish Search Optimizer (JSO) [6], Slim Mould Optimizer (SMA) [7], White Shark Optimizer (WSO) [8], Gorilla Troops Optimization (GTO) [9], Gaussian Bare-bones Levy Circulatory System-Based Optimization (GBLCSBO) [10], Dwarf Mongoose Optimizer (DMO) [11], and Self-Adaptive Wild Geese Algorithm (SAWGA) [12].

This paper examines the application of a nature-inspired algorithm, EEFO, to address the OPF problem using a mix of thermal, wind, and solar units in a large-scale transmission network. The simulation results are compared with the last two articles that deal with the same power system and generators but different optimization algorithms. The objective functions were also maintained to show the effectiveness of this new algorithm over existing ones.

II. Materials and Methods

1. Multi-objective function

The multi-objective function consists of minimizing the TGC, the Active Power Losses (APLs), the Voltage Deviation (VD), and emission effects.

- **Minimization of total generation cost:**

The fuel cost of a Thermal Generator (TG) can be expressed as [9]:

$$C_T(P_{TG}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{TG}} (a_i + b_i P_{TGi} + c_i P_{TGi}^2) \quad (\$/h) \quad (1)$$

Where N_{TG} indicates the number of TGs, a_i , b_i , c_i represent the cost coefficients corresponding to i-th TG producing power output P_{TGi} .

To model the cost function of a TG precisely, the valve point effect must be included as a sinusoidal function, added to the previous equation, and written again as follows [13]:

$$C_T(P_{TG}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{TG}} a_i + b_i P_{TGi} + c_i P_{TGi}^2 + \left| d_i \times \sin \left(e_i \left(P_{TGi}^{\min} - P_{TG} \right) \right) \right| \quad (\$/h) \quad (2)$$

Where d_i and e_i denote the coefficients of the valve point effect, P_{TGi}^{\min} is the minimum power related to i-Th TG.

The cost of wind and solar power is formulated in equations (3) and (4), respectively [14]:

$$C_{WG} = \sum_{j=1}^{N_{WG}} \left[C_{w,j}(P_{ws,j}) + C_{Rw,j}(P_{ws,j} - P_{wav,j}) + C_{Pw,j}(P_{wav,j} - P_{ws,j}) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$C_{SG} = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{SG}} \left[C_{s,k}(P_{ss,k}) + C_{Rs,k}(P_{ss,k} - P_{sav,k}) + C_{Ps,k}(P_{sav,k} - P_{ss,k}) \right] \quad (4)$$

Where, N_{WG} and N_{SG} are the number of wind and solar generators, respectively. $C_{w,j}$ and $C_{s,k}$ represent the direct cost of the j-th wind generator (WG) and the k-th solar generator, respectively. $P_{ws,j}$ and $P_{ss,k}$ are the scheduled power of wind and solar generators, respectively.

$C_{Rw,j}$ and $C_{Rs,k}$ denote the reserve cost of wind and solar generators, respectively. $P_{wav,j}$ and $P_{sav,k}$ represent the actual available power of wind and solar generators, respectively. $C_{Pw,j}$ and $C_{Ps,k}$ are the penalty cost of the wind and solar generators, respectively.

- **Minimization of active power losses:**

The APLs or real power losses, are modeled as [1]:

$$P_L = \sum_{k=1}^{N_L} G_k \left[|V_i|^2 + |V_j|^2 - 2|V_i||V_j|\cos(\sigma_i - \sigma_j) \right] \quad (5)$$

Where N_L is the number of lines in the power system, G_k represents the conductivity of the line k, which links buses i and j, $|V|$ and σ denote the polar form of the bus voltage.

- **Minimization of emission effects:**

Many harmful emissions are generated from conventional power plants, like carbon dioxide (CO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). These gases rise with the increase in power produced. They are calculated in t/h and expressed by [8]:

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} \left[(a_i + b_i P_{G,i} + c_i P_{G,i}^2) \times 0.01 + \omega_i e^{(P_{G,i} \mu_i)} \right] \quad (6)$$

Where, a_i , b_i , c_i , ω_i and μ_i and μ_i represent the emission coefficients of the i-th thermal unit. To reduce greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, many governments are imposing a carbon tax to put pressure on companies to reduce emissions and switch to renewables, the emission cost C_E in \$/h is presented as:

$$C_E = C_T \cdot E \quad (\$/h) \quad (7)$$

Where, C_T is the carbon tax.

- **Minimization of voltage deviation:**

The VD refers to the change in the bus's voltage magnitude in comparison with its nominal value; it is expressed as [15]:

$$VD = \sum_{j=1}^{N_L} |V_k - 1| \quad (8)$$

Where V_K is the voltage magnitude of the K-th bus and N_L is the number of buses.

2. Constraints

- **Equality constraints:**

Equality restrictions ensure that the power produced on one side is equal to the demand and the losses on the other side. Which is expressed in the following equations [16]:

$$P_{Gi} - P_{Di} = |V_i| \sum_{j=1}^{NB} |V_j| \left[G_{i,j} \cos(\sigma_{i,j}) + B_{i,j} \sin(\sigma_{i,j}) \right] \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{Gi} - Q_{Di} = |V_i| \sum_{j=1}^{NB} |V_j| \left[G_{i,j} \sin(\sigma_{i,j}) - B_{i,j} \cos(\sigma_{i,j}) \right] \quad (10)$$

Where P_{Gi} and Q_{Gi} are the active and reactive power generated, respectively, at the bus i. P_{Di} and Q_{Di} represents the demand for active and reactive power, respectively, at the bus i. $G_{j,i}$ and $B_{j,i}$ denotes the conductance and susceptance, respectively, between two buses i and j.

- **Inequality constraints:**

Inequality restrictions are the limitations of elements within the power system, besides the security constraints associated with lines and buses. The active and reactive power outputs and the voltage limits are restricted by specific upper and lower limits [7].

$$P_{TGi}^{\min} \leq P_{TGi} \leq P_{TGi}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_G \quad (11)$$

$$P_{Ws,j}^{\min} \leq P_{Ws,j} \leq P_{Ws,j}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_W \quad (12)$$

$$P_{Ss,k}^{\min} \leq P_{Ss,k} \leq P_{Ss,k}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_S \quad (13)$$

$$Q_{TGi}^{\min} \leq Q_{TGi} \leq Q_{TGi}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_T \quad (14)$$

$$Q_{Ws,j}^{\min} \leq Q_{Ws,j} \leq Q_{Ws,j}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_W \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{Ss,k}^{\min} \leq Q_{Ss,k} \leq Q_{Ss,k}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_S \quad (16)$$

$$V_{T,i}^{\min} \leq V_{T,i} \leq V_{T,i}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_T \quad (17)$$

Equations (11), (12), and (13) represent the limits of active power from thermal, wind, and SPV generators, respectively. Equations (14), (15), and (16) denote the limits of reactive power from thermal, wind, and solar generators, respectively. Equation. (17) Is the voltage limit of generator buses?

Line and load bus voltages are defined as follows [12]:

$$V_{Li}^{\min} \leq V_{Li} \leq V_{Li}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_L \quad (18)$$

$$S_{li} \leq S_{li}^{\max} \quad i=1,2,3,\dots,N_l \quad (19)$$

S_{li} and S_{li}^{\max} refer to the apparent power and its maximum boundary of the i -th line, respectively. V_{Li}^{\min} and V_{Li}^{\max} represent the lower and upper limits of the voltage magnitude. N_l and N_L are the numbers of the transmission line and the load bus, respectively.

III. Proposed EEFO Algorithm

An electric eel is a type of fish that lives in freshwater, mainly in South America, and more specifically in the Amazon basin. The most interesting thing about electric eels is their ability to produce electricity. An adult eel can generate a voltage that ranges between 300 and 800 volts. To release this powerful discharge, eels have three pairs of abdominal organs, as shown in Figure 1. Each organ contains thousands of cells, called electrocytes. These cells can store electricity, like batteries. Eels often generate low electric charges around 10 volts to navigate, communicate with each other, and find prey since they have poor eyesight. The high charges are used not only as a weapon to hunt prey but also as a defense mechanism against predators [17].

Fig. 1. The exterior and interior anatomy of the electric eel and its main organs [18].

Electric eels have been recently categorized as swarm-based creatures, and according to that, they follow social predation, which requires groups of individuals working together to locate and capture prey [19].

1. EEFO mathematical model

The EEFO algorithm is inspired by the behavior of electric eels and is divided into two phases: exploration and exploitation. The social predations of electric eels include interacting, resting, migrating, and hunting.

Each foraging behavior can be modelled mathematically using the following expressions [17]:

- **Interacting:**

The interaction between eels enables them to navigate towards various places in search space. The interacting behavior is expressed by [20]:

$$\begin{cases} \begin{cases} v_i(t+1) = x_j(t) + c \times (\bar{x}(t) - x_i(t)) p_1 > 0.5 \\ v_i(t+1) = x_j(t) + c \times (x_r(t) - x_i(t)) p_1 \leq 0.5 \end{cases} & \text{fit}(x_j(t)) < \text{fit}(x_i(t)) \\ \begin{cases} v_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + c \times (\bar{x}(t) - x_j(t)) p_2 > 0.5 \\ v_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + c \times (x_r(t) - x_j(t)) p_2 \leq 0.5 \end{cases} & \text{fit}(x_j(t)) \geq \text{fit}(x_i(t)) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Where, p_1 and p_2 denote random numbers between 0 and 1, $\text{fit}(i)$ represent the fitness of the candidate position of the i -th electric eel, x_j indicates the position of an eel selected randomly from the current population where $j \neq i$.

- **Resting:**

Eels will move to the resting place once it is determined. An eel updates both its position toward the resting place as well as the resting position within the resting place. The resting behavior can be formulated as [21]:

$$v_i(t+1) = r_i(t+1) + n_2 \times (r_i(t+1) \text{round}(\text{rand}) \times x_i(t)) \quad (21)$$

$$n_2 \sim N(0,1) \quad (22)$$

Where r_i denotes the resting position, n_2 has a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1.

- **Migrating:**

The following expression is used to update the position of the eels [22]:

$$x_i(t+1) = \begin{cases} x_i(t) & \text{fit}(x_i(t)) \leq \text{fit}(v_i(t+1)) \\ v_i(t+1) & \text{fit}(x_i(t)) > \text{fit}(v_i(t+1)) \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Where $\text{fit}(x_i(t))$ represents the fitness of the i -th electric eel's candidate position. x_i is the position of a randomly selected eel. v_i Denotes the position of a randomly chosen food.

- **Hunting:**

During the hunting phase, the eel swiftly identifies the prey's position. and coils itself to bring its head and tail together, with the prey in between. This coiling action results in the emission of a high-voltage current around the eel. The curling behavior performed by eels can be expressed as [17]:

$$v_i(t+1) = H_{prey}(t+1) + \eta \times (H_{prey}(t+1) - \text{round}(\text{rand}) \times x_i(t)) \quad (24)$$

Where η is the curling factor, which is represented as:

$$\eta = e^{\frac{r_5(1-t)}{T}} \cos(2\pi r_5) \quad (25)$$

Where r_5 is a random number between 0 and 1.

2. Transition from exploration to exploitation

The choice between exploration and exploitation is guided by the eel's energy factor value. This energy factor is formally characterized as [23]:

$$E(t) = 4 \sin\left(1 - \frac{t}{T}\right) \ln \frac{1}{r_8} \quad (26)$$

Where r_8 denotes a random number between 0 and 1. Exploration takes place in early iterations with high probability, whereas exploitation becomes predominant in the latter half.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of EEFO [17].

IV. Results and Discussion

The suggested EEFO method was implemented using MATLAB 2021 on a laptop computer characterized by an Intel Core i5 microprocessor with an execution speed of 2.6 GHz and a RAM memory of 4 GB. The parameters concerning the setting of the algorithm consist of a population of 30 individuals and a maximum iteration of 300.

To show the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, we integrate a mix of conventional and renewable sources that consist of three thermal generators, two wind farms, and one SPV plant. The test system used is the modified IEEE 30-bus, which has 30 buses and 41 branches. The next table contains more details [14], [24]:

Table 1. Parameters of the modified IEEE 30-bus test system.

Item	Number	detail
Transformers with Tap Changers	4	Branches 11, 12, 15, and 36
Thermal Generators	3	Buses: 1 (slack), 2, and 8
Wind Generators	2	Buses: 5 and 11
SPV Generator	1	Bus 13

Item	Number	detail
Load Buses	24	[0.95 – 1.05] p.u.
Generators	6	[0.95 – 1.1] p.u.

The following tables denote the parameters of both thermal and renewable generators.

Table 2. Cost coefficients and emissions of the TGs.

	Thermal Generators		
	TG1 (Bus 1)	TG2 (Bus 2)	TG3 (Bus 8)
a	0	0	0
b	2	1.75	3.25
c	0.38	0.0175	0.0083
d	18	16	12
e	0.037	0.38	0.045
α	0.04091	0.02543	0.05326
β	-0.05554	-0.06047	-0.03550
γ	0.06490	0.05638	0.03380
ω	0.0002	0.0005	0.0020
μ	6.667	3.333	2.000

Table 3. Parameters of wind generators.

	Wind Generators	
	WG1 (Bus 5)	WG2 (Bus 11)
Number of Turbines	25	20
Rated Power (MW)	75	60
Weibull PDF Parameters	k = 2, c = 9	k = 2, c = 10
Weibull Mean	v = 7.796	v = 8.862

Table 4. Parameters of the SPV Generator.

SPV Generator (Bus 13)	
Rated Power (MW)	50
Lognormal PDF Parameters	$\mu = 6, \sigma = 0.6$
Lognormal Mean	G = 486 W/m ²

The Weibull fitting curve and the wind distribution frequency are defined using the Monte Carlo method after running 8000 samples [4], as shown in figures 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. The distribution of wind speed for the wind generator at bus 5.

Fig. 4. The distribution of wind speed for the wind generator at bus 11.

To define the SPV unit output power, we execute the Monte-Carlo method with a sample of 8000 scenarios [24]. The lognormal PDF fitting curve and the distribution of solar irradiance are obtained and displayed in Figure 5.

Fig.5. The distribution of the solar irradiance for the SPV unit at bus 13.

Fig. 6. The active power from the SPV unit at bus 13.

The following tables represent the final results obtained after the simulations for each case of study:

Table 5. results of the OPF solution for case 1.

	Case 1		
	KOA [25]	SaBO [26]	EEFO
Total Generation Cost (\$/h)	781.3568	781.2363	781.1981
Power Losses (MW)	5.7082	5.6908	5.7141
Voltage Deviation (p.u.)	0.48188	0.47550	0.45588
Emissions (t/h)	1.76295	1.76195	1.76137

According to the results presented in case 1, EEFO outperforms previous algorithms, with the lowest TGC of 781.1981 \$/h, compared with 781.3568 for KOA and 781.2363 for SaBO. The VD was also reduced to 0.45588 p.u., and the emissions were decreased to 1.76137 t/h.

Table 6. Results of the OPF solution for case 2

	Case 2		
	KOA [25]	SaBO [26]	EEFO
Total Generation Cost (\$/h)	810.0663	809.7452	792.6531
Power Losses (MW)	5.2011	5.2021	5.1940
Voltage Deviation (p.u.)	0.48459	0.48336	0.47607
Emissions (t/h)	0.89502	0.89945	0.86505

For the second case, emissions were reduced to 0.86505 t/h for EEFO, compared with 0.89502 t/h for KOA and 0.8945 t/h for SaBO. TGC, power losses, and VD were also minimized at 792.6531 \$/h, 5.1940 MW, and 0.47607 p.u., respectively, achieving the best results for all objectives.

V. Conclusion

The multi-objective function treated in this paper consisted of minimizing the total generation cost, active power losses, voltage deviation, and emission effects like CO₂, SO₂, and NO_x. These objectives are divided into two main cases: the first is the reduction of TGC, and the second is the minimization of generation cost, including emission effects. The test system is the modified IEEE 30-bus alternative current (AC) network. The results of the simulation show an impressive performance of the proposed EEFO algorithm, which balances exploration and exploitation while avoiding the trap of local optima. This is evident by the reduction of the TGC, APLs, VD, and emissions all at the same time in cases 1 and 2 (excluding APLs in case 1), overtaking other competing algorithms like KOA and SaBO. The robustness of EEFO highlights its ability to be used in several types of power systems for future studies, such as distribution networks and microgrids. It can also be implemented in the planning and management of electric vehicle charging stations, battery storage systems, and DC networks.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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